

INFORMATION ABOUT COMPUTER SCIENCE

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Annotation: *Informatics (French Informatique; English Computer science) is the science of methods and processes for collecting, storing, processing, transmitting, analyzing and evaluating information using computer technologies that make it possible to use it for decision-making*

Key words: *Computer science includes disciplines related to the processing of information in computers and networks: both abstract, such as the analysis of algorithms, and specific, such as the development of programming languages and data transfer protocols.*

Research topics in computer science are the following questions: what can and cannot be implemented in programs and databases (computability theory and artificial intelligence), how to solve specific computational and information problems with maximum efficiency (computation complexity theory), in what form should and recover information of a specific kind (structures and databases), how programs and people should interact with each other (user interface and programming languages and knowledge representation), etc.

German term. Informatik was introduced by the German specialist Karl Steinbuch in the 1957 article Informatik: Automatische Informationsverarbeitung (Informatics: Automatic Information Processing)

The term "Computer science" appeared in 1959 in the scientific journal Communications of the ACM[3], in which Louis Fein advocated the creation of a Graduate School in Computer Sciences (higher school in computer science) similar to Harvard Business School, established in 1921[4][specify]. Justifying such a name for the school, Louis Fein referred to Management science ("Management Science"), which, like computer science, has an applied and interdisciplinary character, while it has features characteristic of a scientific discipline. The efforts of Louis Fein, numerical analyst George Forsyth[en] and others were successful: universities went on to create programs related to computer science, starting with Purdue University

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in 1962 The French term "informatique" was introduced in 1962 by Philippe Dreyfus, who also offered translations into a number of other European languages.

The terms "informology" and "informatics" were proposed in 1962 by Alexander Kharkevich, Corresponding Member of the USSR Academy of Sciences. The foundations of computer science as a science were outlined in the 1965 book *Fundamentals of Scientific Information*, which was republished in 1968 under the title *Fundamentals of Computer Science*

Despite its English name (Eng. Computer Science - computer science), most of the scientific fields related to computer science do not include the study of computers themselves. As a result, several alternative names have been proposed[7]. Some faculties of major universities prefer the term computing science to emphasize the difference between the terms. Danish scientist Peter Naur coined the term datalogy[8] to reflect the fact that the scientific discipline operates with data and deals with data processing, although not necessarily with the use of computers. The first scientific institution to include this term in the name was the Department of Datalogy (Datalogy) at the University of Copenhagen, founded in 1969, where Peter Naur worked, who became the first professor in datalogy (datalogy). This term is used mainly in Scandinavian countries. In the rest of Europe, terms are often used, derived from the abbreviated translation of the phrases "automatic information" (automatic information) (for example, *informazione automatica* in Italian) and "information and mathematics" (information and mathematics), for example, *informatique* (France), *Informatik* (Germany), *informatica* (Italy, Netherlands), *informática* (Spain, Portugal), *informatika* (in Slavic languages) or *pliroforiki* (πληροφορική, meaning informatics) are in Greece. Similar words have also been adopted in the UK, such as the School of Computer Science at the University of Edinburgh

In Russian, English, French and German in the 1960s there was a tendency to replace the term "documentation" with terms based on the word "information"[10]. In Russian, a derivative of the term "documentation" has become documentary and the terms scientific and scientific and technical information have become widespread.

In France, the term officially came into use in 1966[11]. In German, the term is German. *Informatik* initially had a dual meaning. So, in Germany[10] and Great Britain[1] it was in the meaning of "computer science", that is, it meant everything related to the use of computers, and in the GDR, as well as mainly in Europe, it denoted science according to the French and Russian models .

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It is believed that the terms "informatics" in European countries and "informatics" in Russian are understood as a direction called "computer science" in English. The term "information science" is close to another direction devoted to the study of the structure and general properties of objective (scientific) information, sometimes called documentary science (documentary informatics) or automatic analysis of documents

It is generally accepted that Walter F. Bauer, the founder of Informatics Inc., independently introduced the term "informatics" into the English language. In the US, the term is now English. informatics is concerned with applied computing or data processing in the context of another field[12], such as bioinformatics ("bioinformatics") and geoinformatics ("geoinformatics"). Many dictionaries equate informatics and computer science with computer science. In the UNESCO thesaurus "Informatics - Informatics" is given as a synonym for the translation "Computer science - Computer science"

The earliest foundations for what would become computer science predate the invention of the modern digital computer. Machines for calculating several arithmetic problems, such as abacus, have existed since antiquity, assisting in such calculations as multiplication and division.

Blaise Pascal designed and assembled the first working mechanical calculator, known as Pascal's calculator, in 1642

In 1673, Gottfried Leibniz demonstrated a mechanical calculator (arithmometer) called the Stepped Reckoner[23]. He can be considered the first computer scientist and information theorist, because, among other things, he also described the binary (binary) number system.

In 1820, Thomas de Colmar[en] launched the industrial production of a mechanical calculator after he created his simplified arithmometer, which was the first calculating machine strong and reliable enough for daily use. Charles Babbage began designing the first automatic mechanical calculator, his Difference Engine, in 1822, which eventually gave him the idea for the first programmable mechanical calculator, his Analytical Engine.

He began work on this machine in 1834, and in less than two years many of the main features of the modern computer were formulated. The most important step was the use of punched cards made on the Jacquard loom [24], which opened up endless possibilities for programming [25]. In 1843, while translating a French article on an analytical machine, Ada Lovelace wrote in one of her many notes an algorithm for calculating Bernoulli numbers, which is considered the first computer program

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Around 1885, Herman Hollerith invented the tabulator, which used punched cards to process statistical information; his company eventually became part of IBM. In 1937, a hundred years after Babbage's pipe dream, Howard Aiken persuaded IBM, which made all kinds of punched card hardware[27] and was involved in the calculator business, to develop its giant ASCC/Harvard Mark I programmable calculator based on analytics. Babbage's machine, which in turn used punched cards and a central computing unit. It was said about the finished car: "Babbage's dream came true"

In the 1940s, with the advent of new and more powerful computing machines, the term computer began to refer to these machines, and not to people involved in calculations (now the word "computer" is rarely used in this sense) [29]. When it became clear that computers could be used for more than just mathematical calculations, the field of computer science research expanded to include the study of computing in general. Computer science gained the status of an independent scientific discipline in the 1950s and early 1960s [30] [31]. The world's first degree in computer science, the Cambridge Diploma in Computer Science, was awarded at the Cambridge University Computer Laboratory in 1953. The first such curriculum in the United States appeared at Purdue University in 1962[32]. With the spread of computers, many new self-sufficient scientific directions have arisen based on computing using computers.

Few people initially could have imagined that computers themselves would become the subject of scientific research, but in the late 1950s this opinion spread among the majority of scientists [33]. The now well-known IBM brand was one of the participants in the computer science revolution at that time. IBM (short for International Business Machines) released the IBM 704[34] and later the IBM 709[35] computers, which were already in widespread use while these devices were being studied and tested. "Nevertheless, working with (computer) IBM was full of disappointments ... if there was an error in one letter of one instruction, the program "fell" and had to start all over again" [33]. In the late 1950s, computer science as a discipline was still in its infancy,[36] and such problems were commonplace.

Over time, significant progress has been made in the usability and efficiency of computing technology. In modern society, there is a clear transition among users of computer technology: from its use only by experts and specialists to the use of everyone and everyone. Initially, computers were very expensive and in order to use them effectively, the help of specialists was needed. When computers became

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more common and affordable, then less help from specialists was required to solve common tasks.

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